

A Naive Implementation of Logical Expression in Quantum Computing

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Abstract—In this paper, we present a straightforward implementation of a logical expression in quantum computing. We develop a quantum oracle for our logical expression and implement it using Grover’s algorithm. The logical expression comprises two variables and two clauses involving the XOR and AND operators. For this expression, we require two qubits as variables, one qubit as the oracle, and one qubit as an ancilla. Additionally, we utilise CNOT and Toffoli gates to construct the quantum oracle. We then design its quantum circuit and execute it on a simulator. The implementation yields the quantum state of a two-qubit quantum system as the solution to our logical expression.

Keywords: Grover’s algorithm, logical expression, quantum oracle, quantum computing.

I. INTRODUCTION

A logical expression consists of variables combined through logical operators, evaluating to either true or false. For example, the expression $A \text{ AND } B$ involves two variables, A and B , and is true only when both A and B are true. To represent this in a truth table, three columns are needed: A , B , and $A \text{ AND } B$, with four rows for the possible input combinations: $A = 0, B = 0$; $A = 1, B = 0$; $A = 0, B = 1$; and $A = 1, B = 1$. Another example is the expression $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } (C \text{ AND } D)$, which involves four variables: A , B , C , and D . This expression is true when either A or B is true (but not both) and both C and D are true. To depict this in a truth table, seven columns are required: A , B , C , D , $A \text{ XOR } B$, $C \text{ AND } D$, and $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } (C \text{ AND } D)$, with sixteen rows to cover all possible input combinations. As the number of variables and logical combinations in an expression increases, the computational complexity for processing it also grows significantly.

Quantum computing and quantum algorithms are advancing rapidly and becoming more of a reality. The satisfiability problems for logical or Boolean expressions can also be solved using quantum computing. Reference [1] presents the use of Grover’s quantum search algorithm to solve Boolean satisfiability problems, while reference [2] evaluates the use of quantum computing to solve arbitrary instances of the exactly-1 k -SAT problem. Furthermore, reference [3] describes the procedure for solving the 3-SAT problem by combining a quantum search algorithm with the DPLL algorithm, and reference [4] proposes a novel algorithm to apply Grover’s algorithm to 3-SAT problems using a small number of qubits. A step-by-step

Table I. TRUTH TABLE OF $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$

A	B	$A \text{ XOR } B$	$(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$
0	0	0	0
1	0	1	0
0	1	1	1
1	1	0	0

implementation of a logical expression using Grover’s algorithm is also described clearly in reference [5], and a quantum solution for the SAT problem in Qiskit and IBM Q is proposed in [6].

In this paper, we perform a naive implementation of a logical expression using Grover’s algorithm. We develop a quantum oracle and a quantum circuit to satisfy our logical expression. To carry out our quantum circuit and code, we utilise IBM’s Qiskit [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12].

The paper is comprised of four sections: introduction, implementation, results and discussion, and conclusion. The introduction provides brief information on logical expressions and their execution on quantum computing. The implementation section presents a step-by-step account of our straightforward implementation of logical expressions in quantum computing. This section contains three subsections, namely our logical expression, Grover’s algorithm, and running the quantum circuit. The third section, results and discussion, presents and analyses the results of our implementation. Finally, the conclusion summarises the work we have carried out.

II. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Our Logical Expression

In our work, we choose the formula $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$ as our logical expression. This expression has two variables, A and B , and two clauses involving the XOR and AND operators. The truth table for the expression is shown in Table I. From Table I, it can be seen that the expression is true if A is false and B is true.

B. Grover’s Algorithm

Practically, Grover’s algorithm consists of four steps: initialisation, the oracle, the diffusion transform, and measurement [5], [7], [13]. The circuit diagram for Grover’s algorithm is presented in Figure 1 [13], [14].

Figure 1. Circuit diagram for Grover's algorithm

Figure 2. Quantum circuit for 2-qubit Grover's algorithm initialisation

1) *Initialisation:* The first step in implementing Grover's algorithm in quantum computing is initialisation. Our logical expression has two variables, A and B , so we require two qubits to represent these variables. Qubit q_0 represents variable A , and qubit q_1 represents variable B . We also require a third qubit, q_2 . Both qubits q_0 and q_1 are in the state $|0\rangle$, while qubit q_2 is in the state $|1\rangle$. The Hadamard gate is then applied to every qubit. This initialisation step can be visualised in the quantum circuit shown in Figure 2.

2) *Our Oracle:* In quantum computing, the XOR and AND operators can be represented by CNOT and Toffoli gates, respectively [7]. By combining these two gates, we can create a quantum circuit for the logic $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$, as shown in Figure 3. This circuit requires qubit q_3 as an ancilla.

Now we are going to examine the quantum circuit. First, we assume that q_0 and q_1 are in the state $|0\rangle$. In the first column of the circuit, there is a CNOT gate where q_1 acts as the control and q_0 as the target. Since $q_1 = |0\rangle$, q_0 remains in the state $|0\rangle$. In the second column, there is a Toffoli gate where q_0 and q_1 act as controls and q_3 is the target. Here, with $q_0 = q_1 = |0\rangle$, q_3 remains in the state $|0\rangle$.

Second, we assume that q_0 is $|1\rangle$ and q_1 is $|0\rangle$. After applying the CNOT gate, $q_1 = |0\rangle$ and $q_0 = |1\rangle$. Applying these states to the Toffoli gate in the second column results in $q_3 = |0\rangle$.

Third, we set q_0 as $|0\rangle$ and q_1 as $|1\rangle$. After applying the CNOT gate, where $q_1 = |1\rangle$, qubit q_0 becomes $|1\rangle$, and q_3 becomes $|1\rangle$ as the output of the Toffoli gate.

Finally, when both q_0 and q_1 are in the state $|1\rangle$, applying the CNOT gate changes q_0 to $|0\rangle$ while q_1 remains $|1\rangle$. Applying these states to the Toffoli gate in the second column yields $q_3 = |0\rangle$.

Figure 3. Quantum circuit for the logic $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$

Figure 4. Oracle for the logical expression $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$

Figure 5. Diffusion transform of 2-qubit Grover's algorithm

The next step is modifying the quantum circuit to serve as an oracle for the logical expression. We add a Z gate to the ancilla qubit q_3 and then uncompute this ancilla by running the circuit in reverse order. This oracle is shown in Figure 4.

3) *Diffusion Transform:* The quantum circuit for the diffusion transform of the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm is shown in Figure 5 [7]. To analyse it by calculating its matrix representation, we use the equation $2|0\rangle\langle 0| - I$ obtained from the circuit diagram for Grover's algorithm in Figure 1. Since it is a 2-qubit quantum system, $n = 2$, we can write the ket $|0\rangle|0\rangle$ as $|00\rangle$ and the bra $\langle 0|\langle 0|$ as $\langle 00|$. In quantum mechanics, $|\psi\rangle$ is a column vector, and $\langle\psi|$ is the complex conjugate transpose of $|\psi\rangle$, so we can calculate the matrix representation of $2|00\rangle\langle 00| - I_2$. We also compute the matrix representation of the quantum gate $CZ(Z \otimes Z)$ from Figure 5. Both calculations yield the matrix shown in (1).

$$2|00\rangle\langle 00| - I_2 = CZ(Z \otimes Z) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

4) *Measurement:* The fourth step is measurement. We require two classical registers, and the measurement circuit for the 2-qubit quantum system is shown in Figure 6.

C. Running the Quantum Circuit

Combining the circuits of initialisation (Figure 2), oracle (Figure 4), diffusion transform (Figure 5), and measurement (Figure 6) produces a quantum circuit for Grover's algorithm to satisfy the logical expression $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$. We then execute this quantum circuit on a simulator with the number of shots set to 100.

Figure 6. Measurement for 2-qubit quantum system

Figure 7. The probability of measuring the quantum states produced by our circuit

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The outputs of quantum computing can be Bloch multivectors, state vectors, density matrices, or histograms. In this paper, we focus on the histogram of probabilities for each quantum state as the measurement outcome. The logical expression $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$ has two variables, A and B , so we need two qubits to represent these variables. Qubit q_0 represents variable A , and qubit q_1 represents variable B , as discussed previously in II-B1. This 2-qubit quantum system has four states in the form of ket $|q_1 q_0\rangle$, namely $|00\rangle$, $|01\rangle$, $|10\rangle$, and $|11\rangle$. In quantum mechanics, it can be written as $|\psi\rangle = \alpha|00\rangle + \beta|01\rangle + \gamma|10\rangle + \delta|11\rangle$, where $|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 + |\gamma|^2 + |\delta|^2 = 1$. The values of $|\alpha|^2$, $|\beta|^2$, $|\gamma|^2$, and $|\delta|^2$ are the probabilities of finding the states $|00\rangle$, $|01\rangle$, $|10\rangle$, and $|11\rangle$, respectively.

Figure 7 shows that running our quantum circuit on the simulator yields the quantum state $|10\rangle$ with a frequency of 100. This means the probability of finding the state $|10\rangle$ is 1, and this state corresponds to the solution of our logical expression. The probability value is obtained by dividing the frequency by the number of shots.

The quantum state $|10\rangle$ means qubit $q_0 = 0$ and $q_1 = 1$ where q_0 represents variable A and q_1 represents variable B . Thus, our logical expression $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$ is satisfied when A is 0, or false, and B is 1, or true. This quantum computing result matches the classical solution, where the logical expression $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$ equals 1 if $A = 0$ and $B = 1$, as shown in the truth table in Table I.

As an additional implementation, we also develop quantum oracles for the logical expressions $(\neg A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$, $(A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$, and $(\neg A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$. For the expression $(\neg A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$, we add NOT gates to the first and last column of qubit q_0 in the oracle. Meanwhile for the expression $(A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$, we add NOT gates to the first and last column of qubit q_1 in the oracle. Finally, for the expression $(\neg A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$, we add NOT gates to the first and last columns of both qubit q_0 and q_1 in the oracle. These oracles are shown in Figures 8, 9, and 10.

Figure 8. Oracle for the logical expression $(\neg A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$

Figure 9. Oracle for the logical expression $(A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$

Running the oracles using Grover's algorithm and their Qiskit codes on the simulator produces the following results: state $|11\rangle$ for $(\neg A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$, state $|00\rangle$ for $(A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$, and state $|01\rangle$ for $(\neg A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$. The first state $|11\rangle$, means $A = 1$ and $B = 1$; the second state $|00\rangle$, indicates $A = 0$ and $B = 0$; and the third state $|01\rangle$, denotes $A = 1$ and $B = 0$. These three combinations of variables A and B are the solutions for the expressions $(\neg A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$, $(A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$, and $(\neg A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$, respectively.

IV. CONCLUSION

In our naive implementation of the logical expression in quantum computing, we choose the formula $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$ as our logical expression. We develop our quantum oracle and its quantum circuit using Grover's algorithm to satisfy this expression. Our oracle consists of two qubits, q_0 and q_1 , which represent variables A and B , and one qubit, q_3 , as an ancilla. The oracle includes two CNOT gates, two Toffoli gates, and one Z gate. We then execute the quantum circuit on a simulator with 100 shots. As a result, running our quantum circuit and Qiskit code on the simulator yields the quantum state $|10\rangle$ with a probability of 1 as the measurement outcome. From this, we conclude that the quantum state $|10\rangle$ is the solution to our logical expression. The state $|10\rangle$ indicates $q_0 = 0$ and $q_1 = 1$; qubit q_0 represents variable A , and qubit q_1 denotes variable B . Thus, our logical expression $(A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$ is satisfied when A is 0 (false) and B is 1 (true). As an additional implementation, we also develop oracles for the logical expressions $(\neg A \text{ XOR } B) \text{ AND } B$, $(A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$, and $(\neg A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$. Running these oracles using Grover's algorithm and their Qiskit codes on the simulator produces the states $|11\rangle$, $|00\rangle$, and $|01\rangle$, respectively, as the results.

Figure 10. Oracle for the logical expression $(\neg A \text{ XOR } \neg B) \text{ AND } \neg B$

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